

VOCABULARY TEACHING STRATEGIES BASED ON CREATIVE APPROACHES

Ubaydullayev Nodirbek

Student, English Philology Faculty

Uzbek State World Languages University

e-mail: nodirbekubaydullayev0@gmail.com

Scientific advisor: D. Khamidova

Teacher, English Philology Faculty

Uzbek State World Languages University

e-mail: d.xamidova@uzswlu.ru

dhamidova10@gmail.com

Abstract

Today, educational issues are being widely paid attention to. Therefore, the development of the vocabulary, the education of the sound culture of speech, the formation of grammatical correctness are inextricably linked with the mastering of the methods of creating a fluent speech. This article deals with the analysis of various strategies of teaching language aspects, particularly, ways of enriching vocabulary connecting the process with real life values and considering moral characteristics of every individual learner.

Аннотация

Сегодня вопросам образования уделяется широкое внимание. Поэтому развитие словарного запаса, воспитание звуковой культуры речи, формирование грамматической правильности неразрывно связаны с овладением приемами создания беглой речи. В данной статье рассматриваются различные стратегии обучения языковым аспектам, в частности, способы обогащения словарного запаса, связывающие этот процесс с реальными жизненными ценностями и учитывающие моральные характеристики ребенка каждого отдельного обучающегося.

Annotatsiya

Bugungi kunda ta'lim-tarbiya masalalariga keng e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Binobarin, soʻz boyligini rivojlantirish, nutqning tovush madaniyatini tarbiyalash, grammatik toʻgʻrilikni shakllantirish ravon nutq yaratish usullarini egallash bilan uzviy bogʻliqdir. Bu haqda biz ushbu maqolada gaplashamiz. Ushbu maqolada tilni oʻrgatishning turli strategiyalari, xususan, lugʻatni boyitish yoʻllari, jarayonni real hayotiy qadriyatlar bilan bogʻlash va har bir oʻquvchining individual xususiyatlari axloqiy qadriyatlarni hisobga olish masalalari koʻrib chiqilad.

Keywords: *text, listening, speaking, analysis, comparison, didactic tool, educational effectiveness, creativity, figurative movement, interactive method, creative task.*

Ключевые слова: *текст, аудирование, говорение, анализ, сравнение, дидактический инструмент, образовательная эффективность, творчество, образное движение, интерактивный метод, творческое задание*

Kalit soʻzlar: *matn, tinglash, nutq, tahlil, taqqoslash, didaktik vosita, tarbiyaviy samaradorlik, ijodkorlik, obrazli harakat, interfaol usul, ijodiy topshiriq.*

Preschool age from 1979 to the present day the problem of teaching children She language and oz language (Russian, Uzbek). Research objects of Uzbekistan scientists, methodologists, psychologists (F.R. Kodirova, R.M. Kodirova, G.H. Dzhumasheva, D.R.Babaeva, D.Abdurakhimova, L.R.Mirdzhalilova, N.Sh.Nurmuhammedova and others).

The economic, political, social and cultural stability of any society depends on the level of spiritual-ethical, intellectual and professional potential of its citizens. Thinking about the spiritual, moral and professional foundations of the development of Uzbekistan, young people in the conditions of independence who have an independent opinion, who are ideologically trained and whose professional skills are used for the development of our independent country. One of the urgent tasks is the need to educate in a spirit that can mobilize selflessly. Therefore, a

spiritually, morally and professionally fully formed person will have a sense of pride in his homeland, nation, and profession.

Creativity as a category that develops personality is an integral part of human thinking and spirituality. It is manifested not in the diversity of the knowledge a person has, but “in the pursuit of new ideas, reforming and changing established stereotypes, making unexpected and unusual decisions in the process of solving life problems”¹. That is, creativity cannot be achieved by repeating the given knowledge, the main condition is the emergence of a new thought, a new idea in the process of creative thinking. Therefore, imagination plays an important role in the process of creative thinking. This is what Albert Einstein meant when he said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge."²

Moreover, “learning a second language differs according to the situation i.e. learning a second language in a foreign culture or learning a second language in a native culture” [6, 2021]. A learner’s surrounding determines their further interaction in the process. As noted by our scholars, a person's character is formed in the first years of life, and the qualities that appear during this period become a person's second nature. In enriching and activating the vocabulary, its qualitative improvement comes first. It is an antonym (bitter-sweet), synonym (sharp - sharpened, sharp), polysemous (sharp knife, hot pepper, bitter tongue) refers to the understanding of such phenomena and their active use in speech. Children see things, natural phenomena, people's actions , identify their diversity and commonality, and reflect their meaning in speech using words, comparisons, specific verbs, similes that are opposite or close to each other. Methods of choosing a synonym or antonym for a word combination explain to children that words have many meanings. Summarizing names (animals, dishes, transport) are formed based on the comparison of the functions of things.

Vocabulary work is an activity (excursion, demonstration of things) carried out in the process of familiarization with the ever-expanding range of things and events in the world ;

Vocabulary activities are activities based on deepening children's knowledge of surrounding objects and events (acquaintance with qualities, characteristics, unique aspects);

The extent to which children can inherit the national spiritual wealth that is passed from generation to generation in their mother tongue, the ability of the children to master the scientific achievements of their time in the future, their loyalty to the advanced poetic and aesthetic ideals of humanity, that is, independent It depends on the educator that they can become full-fledged builders of a democratic society in Uzbekistan.

Development of vocabulary, education of the sound culture of speech, formation of grammatical correctness, mastering the methods of structuring fluent speech (connectors of sentences, lexical repetitions, means of connecting with the help of synonyms; the structure of description, description, reasoning) is inextricably linked. All aspects of speech, developed on the basis of dialogic communication related to the performance of various functions, are directly related to the formation of language consciousness, and for this, they require a certain form of communication of the child with adults, not only to know the external world and another person. They will need communication aimed at understanding the language itself, its structure and activity.

Cultivating speech is one of the means of artistic expression of the language by mastering the rules of oral and written artistic language: correct pronunciation, accent, grammar, correct use of words. Pedagogical process that represents the development of fluency with effective use. The development of speech in its essence is the norms of oral and written artistic language by a person, including the student: correct pronunciation, accent, grammar, correct use of words pedagogical support with the help of methods and tools that ensure the practical mastery of the rules of language, effective use of artistic means of language expression, the acquisition of fluency, proper guidance, necessary training means taking the necessary measures and leading the process.

By its nature, the concept of "speech development " is often used as an alternative to the concept of "speech development". Especially in the research conducted in Russian, in the literature created in this language, "speech development" is adopted as a basic concept when talking about the transformation of thoughts, experiences (internal speech) into external speech in preschoolers and elementary school students. At this point , it is appropriate to highlight the essence of the concept of "inner speech" : business speech is a mental speech that is not expressed using language and is not written, and it expresses the appeal of a person to himself. Internal speech, like any speech, exhibits its own characteristics. In particular, “internal speech does not have a clear grammatical form , it is formed by means of comprehensible words and complete phrases”³. Before talking about the didactic requirements of speech development, methodical approaches to it, understanding what the term "development" serves to illuminate, allows you to correctly define the direction for the next practical action.

Also, creative thinking means comprehensive thinking about a specific issue, approaching the same point from different angles. The most surprising thing is that the educational process teaches children to think in the same way. It can be seen that the famous inventors and discoverers did not get used to the uniformity of the educational process at school, did not fit into the molds. For example, Albert Einstein was expelled from school or Dmitri Mendeleev got a "three" in chemistry.

Therefore, at each point of the vocabulary teaching process, based on the individual characteristics of each child, it is necessary to skillfully find a way to the heart of each of them with creativity, and effective ways of educational influence on the child's personality. searching, finding and conducting scientific research in this regard is one of the main tasks of pedagogy.

References:

1. Q.A.Abdullaeva and others, The State Education Department of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Primary education j. – T.: 2005. No. 5. P– 4-9.
2. Aminova F. Formation of communication text completion skills. – Tashkent: Science, 2006. P – 100.

3. Aminova F. H. Didactical approach to teaching the student to write a dialogue text: Ped. science. name Dec. avtopef. – T.: UzPFITI. 2007. P– 22.
4. Хамидова, д. (2022, june). Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларидаги иқтисодий терминларнинг лексикографик қиёси муаммо ва ечимлар. «Узбекские национальные образовательные здания теоретическое и практическое создание вопросы" международная научно-практическая конференция (vol. 1, no. 1).
5. Aclonova O.P. Pedagogical support for formation of thinking speed in elementary school students: Ped. science Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in ... diss. avtopef. - KapDU. 2020. P – 49
6. Khamidova, d. M. (2021). Communicative competence in teaching a foreign language through cross-cultural perspective. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 2031-2034.
7. 8. Асқарова М., Матчонов С., Кодипова Ф., Гуломова Х., Бойматова А., Бозопова М., Мухамедова Д. Speaking at the Uzbek language training. - T.: TDPU, 2000. P – 58.
8. Нербова V.V. Zanyatiya po razvitiyu pechi s detmi 4-6 let / Dop.2-e izd. - M.: Ppocveshchenie, 2007. C – 207.
9. Dzhupaev P., Pakhimov B., Kholmatov Sh. New pedagogical technology. - T.: Science, 2005. P – 66
10. Dzhupaev PX, Tolipov O'.Q., Cafarova P.G', Topakulov XO, Inoyatova M.E., Divanova M.C. Dictionary of pedagogical terms. - T.: Science, 2008. P – 198
11. Abdullayeva Q. Cultivating speech. - T.: Teacher, 1980. P – 66
12. Abdullayeva F. The role of international studies such as pisa and timss in improving the quality of the educational system // center nauchnyx publication (bukhdu. en). - 2021. - T. 3. – no. 3.
13. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/335967-the-formation-of-the-creativity-of-stude-2455a505.pdf>

14. <https://bigthink.com/starts-with-a-bang/einstein-famous-quote-misunderstood/>
15. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11229-022-03861-1>